

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SAMSTAD****FIRST NAME: CHRISTINA****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)The author used the following software: MSWord 2013 on Windows 10

STYLE GUIDES AGAINST PLAGIARISM IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In the following response paper, I will discuss the importance of style guides for academic writing. The variety of different rules of style, *The Chicago Manual of Style*, the *WHO Style Guide*, and the *University of Oxford Style Guide*, to mention a few, suggest that there is no universal agreement on one single set of rules. On the contrary, the rules are arbitrary and serve to mark differences between countries, organisations, institutions, departments, and disciplines (EUCLID 2019, 24). This is an identifiable downside to style guides for academic writing, but what are the benefits? I will argue that rules of style, among their other positive aspects, help to avoid plagiarism.

To show this, I will first explain what plagiarism is and give an example of a notable plagiarism case in Germany. Then I will outline how citing prevents plagiarism and illustrate the significance of this writer's tool for academics and other professionals. Finally, I will describe how rules of style help writers to cite correctly, which protects them from committing plagiarism, and how these rules enable readers to understand a citation.

2) THE ELEMENTS OF PLAGIARISM

The EUCLID *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1* points out that; 'plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information' (EUCLID 2019, 6). This definition of plagiarism covers the act of copying paragraphs of someone else's work word for word, as well as the

intentional paraphrasing of somebody's idea in order to pass it off as one's own. Furthermore, other intellectual property such as, but not limited to, statistical data or graphical illustrations can potentially be plagiarised (EUCLID 2019, 5).

Plagiarism is intellectual theft and can have severe consequences, which range from failing a course or a degree to being expelled from an academic institution or community. Therefore, and also because it is unethical, efforts need to be made to avoid any form of plagiarism or even the slightest suspicion of it (ibid.).

A high-profile example that serves to illustrate the severity of ramifications against plagiarists is the case against Karl-Theodor zu Guttenberg, a former German defence minister. Guttenberg finished his dissertation at the University of Bayreuth in 2007. In 2011 however, it came to light that Guttenberg had copied and paraphrased other authors without citing them. Once the media got involved, Guttenberg lost his doctoral degree and had to resign from his political career within a fortnight. Furthermore, legal claims were made against him, which he settled by paying a five-figure fine, and "guttenbergen" became a synonym amongst teenagers for cribbing.

3) PREVENTING PLAGIARISM WITH CITATIONS

A practical method to prevent plagiarism is to cite the author whose work one uses for his or her own academic endeavours. Basically, citing is the parallel opposite of plagiarising, since citing means pointing out the source of the information or the details used whereas plagiarising means to hide it (EUCLID 2019, 6).

Citation is required when quoting other authors or sources as well as when paraphrasing their work. Quotations provide an exact copy of the original. Quoted passages of text appear in quotation marks or, if they exceed a certain length (rules for this vary), in a separate paragraph. There, the quotation should be formatted in a specific and distinct way as a blocked quote, for instance, by using Microsoft Word's quote style (EUCLID 2019, 6-7).

However, quotations should only be inserted if they help to argue the thesis of a paper. Therefore, paraphrasing is the more frequently used form of citation. An author who paraphrases an idea or information uses his or her own words and style. Nevertheless, it is crucial to represent the original correctly and adequately. Paraphrases do not stand out visually like quotations. This makes clear and accurate citation all the more important for paraphrased passages of writing (EUCLID 2019, 7-8).

The above mentioned former German Defence Minister, Karl-Theodor zu Guttenberg, had failed in this area. The investigating committee found that he had paraphrased other authors' publications by changing the original slightly, which made the committee rule that the deceit must have been intentional. In Germany, the Guttenberg scandal set off a whole series of cases against suspected plagiarists. The main protagonists were politicians or other figures of public interest. Regardless of the investigation's outcome, the suspicion alone could damage the individual's reputation. The availability of

academic resources online played a significant role in exposing willful deception. Nowadays, even more academic material is accessible on the internet. Furthermore, there are software tools such as Plagaware, Plagscan, Scribbr, etc. available to check texts for plagiarism. This explains the increased need for academics to protect themselves against charges or even the slightest suspicion of plagiarism.

4) STYLE GUIDES FOR CITATIONS

Style guides offer rules for citation, which provide authors with appropriate tools to reveal the source of information and ideas used in their writing (EUCLID 2019, 11-12). Moreover, these rules enable readers to quickly identify citations – even those that appear as paraphrases – and encourages them to look up the sources to explore their original context.

However, writers do not need to cite every idea or piece of information that they use. General information or ideas that can be found in different sources and therefore count as general knowledge do not have to be cited. This helps avoid an overabundance of citations (EUCLID 2019, 9-10). Writers must give other authors credit for their original ideas though. It is not only common academic practice and an ethical responsibility towards the original author but also an obligation towards the reader, who should be given the opportunity to compare both works.

Citations can appear as in-text citations or as footnotes/endnotes (EUCLID 2019, 6, 11-12). As a reader, I find in-text citations the least distracting with regards to the reading flow; endnotes I find the most disruptive. As an author, I have very limited experience with in-text citations because my former faculties preferred footnotes. However, I also see the merits of in-text citations; especially when writers use applications like Zotero which make citing easy to standardise for everybody.

Although style guides provide clear instructions, the number of different style guides can be confusing both for the writer and the reader. Therefore, it is essential to identify and adhere to the recommended rule of style in one's own academic field (EUCLID 2019, 24-25).

5) CONCLUSION

Due to the number of different style guides, it might be argued that none of them is a reliable and authoritative source, and hence they are all redundant. However, each of them provides a set of rules that a certain community – i.e., a business, an organisation, a university – has agreed on. This offers reassurance and clarity for both users of the rules as well as for readers of their texts. With regards to citations, the use of a style guide means that, on the one hand, the writer can unambiguously indicate quotations and paraphrases. On the other hand, the reader can then easily find and engage with the source material. This proves the thesis of my paper, namely that the use of a style guide provides a reliable tool to guard against plagiarism. Prominent examples of plagiarism, such as Guttenberg's,

could have been easily avoided and will hopefully be prevented in the future by the use of the many tools currently available.

REFERENCES

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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